

APPLYING VXI TECHNOLOGY TO DC POWER SUPPLY PROGRAMMING RESISTORS

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Abstract – The legacy F-16 Analog Tester utilized resistor programmable DC power supplies for application of programmable stimulus. Resistor programmable power supplies, although still available in today's market, are becoming a rarity. The F-16 Analog Test Station Sustainment (FATSS) team decided up front to eliminate reliance on the availability of such devices, and engineer a means to convert the existing resistances to an analog voltage, more compatible with modern power supply programming options.

INTRODUCTION

Many older test systems are equipped with resistor-programmable power supplies, while current technology is geared toward either analog (5 to 10 VDC) or digital (GPIB) programming. The engineer or team of engineers tasked with the replacement of resistor programmable power supplies is faced with an interesting challenge.

In the refurbishment of the Honeywell 2600 Analog Depot Automatic Test Set (ADATS), this challenge was one of many confronting the F-16 Analog Test Station Sustainment (FATSS) team. We set out from the beginning to find a way to incorporate the current technology, readily available from multiple vendors, into the existing legacy hardware and software. This software uses fixed and sometimes programmable resistances (incorporated within the interface hardware) to control voltage and current levels.

This paper will discuss the challenges of the task, the methods investigated, the input and assistance offered by power supply vendors, the path taken towards implementation, and finally, the progress of the chosen solution through hardware source selection, software driver development, prototype

construction, and integration of the hardware and software into the refurbished Automatic Test Equipment (ATE).

Refurbishment Proof of Concept

On March 9, 1994, after many months of discussion among ourselves (the F-16 Analog Software Engineering Section), we set aside some man-hours and begged and borrowed some VXI equipment, and took up the task of running our simplest Test Program Set (TPS) on a VXI based system. The operating system was Windows 3.1.1, using National Instruments LabView version 3.1.1. The sole programmable DC power supply used in the effort was a spare Hewlett Packard 6274B, now no longer produced or supported by HP.

In October 1997, TISAD received funding from our customer, the F-16 Analog Depot Repair Branch (LARP), to perform a refurbishment of the aging ADATS. At this time, a team of 10 engineers was assembled, and one of the first tasks was Hardware Source Selection. In order for competent choices to be made for our eleven DC power supplies, a decision as to the method of remote programming would have to be made immediately.

THE SEARCH FOR AN ANSWER

The Legacy ADATS DC Power

The legacy ADATS contains eleven programmable DC power supplies, manufactured by various vendors, and each model of power supply currently in our ADATS has at some time in the remote to recent past

been declared obsolete, thus unsupportable, by the manufacturer.

The obsolescence of our power supplies has been a matter of concern since even before the proof-of-concept was constructed, this due to our concerns about replacing power supplies on the aging legacy equipment. In the original ADATS design, the DC power supplies rely on a fixed or variable linear resistance physically located within the Interface Test Adapter (ITA).

With no ITA present, or with an ITA not utilizing a particular power supply, the open circuit presented to the resistor programming terminals of the power supply results in an over-maximum voltage condition on each unused power supply (the design circumvents the over-voltage trip protection by wiring a diode in parallel with the programming terminals, which allows a minimal current flow between the terminals).

Sustainment Design Considerations

For the refurbishment, it is desirable to keep our power supplies at zero potential when not in use, both for personnel safety and equipment protection. Taking into account all that we wanted to accomplish with the refurbishment of the DC power supplies, we decided that the best solution would be to use equipment that could read the ITA programming resistors and create a proportionate DC programming voltage to the respective power supply.

Our informal searches for suitable replacements led us to the conclusion that in order to absolutely ensure procurement of and support for our programmable DC power supplies in the future, we would have to find a way to incorporate external DC voltage control of the power supplies in our refurbishment effort.

Investigation of Options

The first bug in the soup for our solution was the fact that the programming resistance could be changed during the execution of a TPS, perhaps by changing a value on the decade resistance unit. This means that in order to implement our solution, we must be able to continually monitor the ITA programming resistances and immediately change the programming voltage in response to a resistance change.

So, it appears that the ingredients for success include: a means of reading a resistance, a means for translating the resistance into a proportionate voltage, and the ability to do so virtually instantaneously.

Knowing about Data Acquisition (DAQ) systems, we hit the books and found that the HP E1419A seemed to meet our requirements.

Capability of the HP E1419A Data Acquisition Module

The HP E1419A is a configurable C-size VXI multifunction measurement and control module. The unit can have its Signal Conditioning Plug-on (SCP) modules programmed at initialization, and the HP E1419 will continually monitor the SCP's.

We configured out HP E1419A with model 1505 constant current sources and model 1501 programmable voltage sources. The 1505 modules output a constant 488uA into the ITA programming resistors, and the resultant voltage drop is read. The voltage drop is then inserted into a specific equation that determines the amount of DC control voltage to be output by the 1501 SCP's into the analog control inputs of the station DC power supplies.

The module operates independently of VXI command and control signals once programmed, so control of the power supplies is moved out of the station computer operating system (and the National Instruments Test Executive) and thus is not susceptible to demands on the station CPU, and does not load the CPU with tasks that could interfere with the operation of the test exec.

For operator and equipment safety, the algorithms programmed into the E1419A will set the DC control voltage to zero when the programming resistance increases past +20% of the maximum allowed value. Until the +20% point is reached (between 100% and 120%), the controller will output the maximum control voltage (usually 10V).